

USE OF THE MIDWIFERY MODEL OF CARE AMONG MIDWIVES IN THE SPECIALIST HOSPITAL, SOKOTO, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Evidence from high-income countries shows that the midwifery model of care improves maternal and neonatal outcomes and is essential for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations. However, its implementation in low and medium income countries (LMICs) remains limited. This study assessed the use of the midwifery model of care among midwives at the Sokoto Specialist Hospital. A descriptive cross-sectional survey was conducted among 60 midwives using a self-administered questionnaire, with data analyzed using SPSS version 26. The study found that 66.67% of the respondents had adequate knowledge of the midwifery model of care, while one-third exhibited knowledge gaps. Attitudes toward the model were generally positive, with strong support for minimal intervention, respect for women's autonomy, and continuous support during labor with a cumulative mean ($\bar{x} = 4.11$). However, actual practice showed low adherence to the midwifery model, as all respondents routinely performed episiotomies, most augmented labor, and fewer applied comprehensive supportive roles. Utilization of the midwifery model was primarily constrained by health system, sociocultural, and political factors, including limited access, inadequate staffing, insufficient funding, and stakeholder resistance, rather than lack of knowledge or confidence among providers. Although most midwives demonstrated knowledge of the midwifery model of care and expressed positive attitudes toward its principles, the actual practice was low, with many continuing to apply aspects of the medical model. Hospital management should provide adequate facilities, ensure access to resources, and support continuous education through workshops, seminars, and conferences to strengthen the midwifery model of care.

Introduction

Midwives are the primary care providers for women during pregnancy, childbirth, and the postpartum period worldwide (Choudhary et al., 2018). Midwife-led continuity of care (MLCC) models, where one midwife or a

small group provides care throughout the maternity continuum, have been shown to improve outcomes, including fewer interventions, more spontaneous births, reduced preterm births, and higher maternal satisfaction (Hildingsson et al., 2021).

According to the International Confederation of Midwives (ICM, 2014), a midwife is a professional who has completed accredited midwifery training, meets global standards, and is licensed to practice. The World Health Organization recognizes midwives as efficient providers of maternal care, particularly in countries such as the Netherlands, Sweden, and New Zealand, where outcomes are among the best globally (Moghasemi et al., 2018). Midwifery care is holistic, addressing the physical, emotional, cultural, and social needs of women (Moghasemi et al., 2018).

MLCC models may take the form of caseload midwifery, where one midwife supports a woman throughout pregnancy, or team midwifery, where a small group shares responsibility (Mose et al., 2023). These models have been well established in countries such as England and Australia (Moghasemi et al., 2018). Theoretical frameworks developed across diverse contexts, including the United States, New Zealand, and Sweden, emphasize woman-centered care and continuity (Lundgren et al., 2022).

Evidence from a Cochrane review indicates that MLCC significantly reduces preterm births, neonatal mortality, and obstetric interventions while improving breastfeeding rates and maternal satisfaction (Sandall et al., 2024; Mose et al., 2023). Despite its proven benefits and WHO/ICM recommendations, the adoption of MLCC in LMICs, including Nigeria, remains limited (Edmonds et al., 2020).

Globally, maternal mortality remains a major concern, with 295,000 deaths in 2017, 94% of which occurred in low- and middle-income countries, predominantly in sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia (WHO, UNICEF, UNFPA, World Bank Group & United Nations Population Division, 2019). Nigeria has one of the highest maternal mortality ratios (MMR) at 545 per 100,000 live births, with marked regional disparities—1,549/100,000 in the northeast compared to 165/100,000 in the southwest (Abimbola et al., 2012). Limited skilled birth attendance, inadequate antenatal coverage, and inequities in maternal and child health indices contribute to these outcomes.

Obstacles to implementing midwifery models in Nigeria include medical dominance, fragmented care, poor workplace culture, and undervaluation of midwifery roles (Sangy et al., 2023). Nonetheless, studies have demonstrated the willingness of midwives to embrace MLCC when organizational support exists, as demonstrated in Ethiopia (Mose et al., 2023).

Given the high maternal mortality burden and underutilization of midwifery-led care, this study aimed to assess the use of the midwifery model of care among midwives in Specialist Hospital Sokoto, Nigeria.

AIM

This study aimed to assess the midwives' knowledge, attitude, and practice of the midwifery model as well as the factors that affect its use in a specialized hospital in Sokoto.

METHODS

Design

A cross-sectional descriptive survey design was employed to assess the use of the midwifery model of care among midwives at the Sokoto Specialist Hospital.

Population, sample, and sampling

The study population comprised all 60 midwives working at Specialist Hospital, Sokoto, at the time of the study. The hospital has a bed capacity of approximately 500 and provides services in medicine, maternity, surgery, ophthalmology, pediatrics, and ENT, among others. Based on Cochrane (2014), a census approach is recommended for populations smaller than 100. Therefore, all 60 midwives were included in the sample.

Instrument for data collection

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire adapted from Ogbuabor and Okoronko (2021). The instrument consisted of 30 items divided into five sections:

Section A: Sociodemographic characteristics (9 items)

Section B: Knowledge of the midwifery model of care (6 items)

Section C: Attitudes toward the Midwifery Care Model (5 items)

Section D: Practice of the midwifery model of care (4 items)

Section E: Factors affecting the utilization of the midwifery model of care (6 items)

Face validity was ensured through literature review to align the items with the study objectives. The content validity was established through an expert review. The items were critically assessed to confirm their relevance, clarity, and comprehensiveness. A pretest was conducted with 10% of the sample, excluding those who participated in the main study. Clarity and comprehension were confirmed by feedback. The instrument demonstrated good reliability (Cronbach's alpha of 0.79, 0.80, and 0.81 for the knowledge, attitude, and practice scales, respectively).

Data Collection

Approval was obtained from the head of the hospital administration and maternity unit. The purpose of the study was explained to the participants during their shifts, after which the questionnaires were distributed. The completed questionnaires were collected for analysis.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics with IBM SPSS version 26.0. Results were presented in frequency tables and percentages. Sociodemographic data were grouped, and frequencies and percentages were computed for each variable, with the highest frequency reported as the category. Frequencies and percentages were calculated for each response option (Yes = 1, No = 0) across all items for the perceived knowledge and practice scales, and levels of knowledge and practice were determined based on the proportion of responses per item. Attitudes toward the midwifery model of care and factors affecting its use were assessed using Likert-scale items to calculate cumulative mean scores.

Ethical Considerations

Permission was obtained from the hospital management. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants after they were briefed on the study's objectives. Participants were assured of confidentiality and anonymity; identifiers were replaced with codes to protect their privacy.

RESULTS

Sociodemographic Data

All respondents were female. The majority (64.29%) were aged 30–39 years, and 78.57% were housewives. More than half (55.35%) had 5–10 years of general work experience, while 82.14% had 5 years of experience in maternity care? Most worked rotational shifts (91.07%). In terms of qualifications, 71.43% held RN/RM, 25.0% held post-basic diplomas, and 3.57% held BNSc degrees. Most respondents (87.50%) practiced Islam.

Knowledge of the Midwifery Care Model

Two-thirds of the respondents (66.67%) demonstrated adequate knowledge of the midwifery model of care, while 33.33% showed knowledge gaps.

Attitude toward the Midwifery Care Model

The findings revealed generally positive attitudes. Respondents agreed that most women can give birth without unnecessary intervention ($\bar{x} = 4.32$) and that they support women in labor without undue interference ($\bar{x} = 4.79$). They also emphasized the importance of women's autonomy during childbirth ($\bar{x} = 4.68$). Although some preferred medical interventions in labor ($\bar{x} = 3.29$), the cumulative mean score ($\bar{x} = 4.11$) indicated an overall positive attitude toward the midwifery model of care.

Practice of the Midwifery Care Model

Despite positive attitudes, the practice was limited. All respondents (100%) reported performing episiotomies and routinely augmented labor (71.43%). While 100% of women stayed with women during labor, only 60.71% applied both traditional and modern supportive roles. Overall, the findings demonstrate suboptimal adherence to the midwifery care model.

Factors Affecting use

Factors affecting use included health system challenges, such as limited access ($\bar{x} = 4.34$), and sociocultural and political constraints ($\bar{x} = 4.66$). Respondents also cited inadequate staffing, insufficient funding, and stakeholders' resistance. However, most disagreed that lack of knowledge or confidence was a major barrier ($\bar{x} = 2.95$).

Discussion

This study found that most respondents were female midwives aged 30–39 years, consistent with the findings of Forster et al. (2016) in Northern Nigeria. The absence of male midwives reflects sociocultural norms in Hausa–Fulani communities, where men rarely work in maternity units. More than two-thirds were housewives, over half had 5–10 years of work experience, and most were junior midwives with RN/RM qualifications. These results are consistent with those of Ogbuabor and Okoronkwo (2021), who reported similar demographic patterns in Enugu.

Knowledge of the midwifery model of care was moderate, with 66.67% demonstrating adequate understanding. This corresponds with the findings of Lundgren et al. (2022), who noted that midwives viewed midwifery model of care as a valuable framework for holistic care, and Moridi et al. (2022), who reported strong knowledge and practice scores in respectful maternity care among Iranian midwives.

Attitudes toward midwifery model of care were generally positive. Respondents valued women's autonomy and supported labor without unnecessary interventions, which is consistent with the findings of Sandall et al. (2016), who observed broad professional interest in midwifery model of care across settings. Similarly, Ogbuabor and Okoronkwo (2021) highlighted that despite systemic challenges, midwives in Enugu emphasized respectful, supportive care.

However, in practice, adherence to midwifery model of care was limited. Routine interventions, such as episiotomy and labor augmentation, were common, echoing the findings of Nilsson et al. (2019), who described tensions between medicalized and midwifery models of care. Comparable trends were observed in global studies, where investment in midwifery has reduced maternal mortality in countries such as Sri Lanka and Malaysia (Podder et al., 2023; Murphy, 2018; Pajalic et al., 2019). However, midwifery model of care implementation does not automatically guarantee significant reductions in interventions without systemic support in Sweden (Lundgren et al., 2022).

The barriers to midwifery model of care use identified in this study included health system constraints, sociocultural and political influences, inadequate staffing, and limited funding. These findings align with those of Probandari et al. (2017) in Indonesia, who reported workload and resource challenges, and Sangy et al. (2023), who emphasized the need for strengthened midwifery education, stakeholder collaboration, and sustainable funding in LMICs.

Overall, this study reinforces the importance of midwifery model of care as a globally recognized, woman-centered model that enhances maternal outcomes. However, systemic, sociopolitical, and organizational barriers continue to limit its full implementation in Nigeria. Strengthening midwifery practice, providing continuous education, and addressing health system challenges are essential for improving maternity care quality.

Conclusion

The study revealed that midwives at Specialist Hospital Sokoto possess an appreciable level of awareness but demonstrate inadequate use of the midwifery model of care in their practice. Only a few midwives applied aspects

of the model during labor management. Therefore, both awareness and use of the midwifery model of care in hospitals and labor wards must be strengthened to achieve optimal implementation. This will enhance care delivery efficiency and effectiveness, ultimately improving maternal outcomes.

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Tables

Table 1: Socio demographic Data (n = 56)

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentages (%)
Age		
20-29	10	17.86
30-39	36	64.29
40-49	10	17.85
Gender		

Male	0	0
Female	56	100
Marital Status		
Single	12	21.43
Other	0	0
Housewife	44	78.57
Working Experience		
< 5 Years	18	32.14
5-10 Years	31	55.35
11-15 Years	5	8.92
>15 Years	2	3.57
Work Experience in Maternity		
< 5 Years	46	82.14
5-10 Years	4	7.14
11-15 Years	5	8.93
>15 Years	1	1.78
Shift Work		
Either Morning or Night	5	8.93
Rotation	51	91.07
Present Rank		
Cno	2	3.57
Acno	8	14.29
Sno	10	17.85
No	36	64.29
Religion		
Islam	49	87.5
Christianity	7	12.5
Other	0	0
Level of education		
Rn/Rm	40	71.43
Post Basic Diploma	14	25
Bnsc	2	3.57

Table 2: Knowledge of the midwifery care model

Variables	Yes		No	
	F	%	F	%
Midwifery models provide words and structure to midwifery	54	96.43	2	3.57
The midwifery model of care is a tool that helps midwives holistically comprehend the birthing woman	50	89.29	6	10.71
Giving birth is a pathological process that requires medical intervention	2	3.57	54	96.43
In midwifery model of care, midwife can rampantly use procedures such as episiotomy and induction of labor.	26	46.42	30	53.57

Birthing is the work of doctors, nurses, midwives, and other experts.	41	73.21	15	26.79
The midwifery model of care is a tool for an extended understanding of what may disturb a woman during labor and birth.	51	91.07	5	8.93
Aggregate percentage		66.67%		33.3%
Total mean				

Table 3: Midwives’ attitudes toward the midwifery model of care

ITEM	SA	A	N	D	SD	X	Remark
Most women can give birth without intervention.	40	5	1	9	1	4.32	Agreed
I support women in labor without unnecessary intervention.	45	11	0	0	0	4.79	Agreed
I prefer medical intervention for women in labor.	2	30	10	10	4	3.29	Agreed
I think women should be allowed to give their preference at birth.	10	26	0	20	0	3.46	Agreed
I respect the autonomy of women during labor	46	2	8	0	0	4.68	Agreed

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Did you perform episiotomy as an intervention?		
Yes	56	100
No	0	0
Not sure	0	0
Total	56	100
2. Which caring role did you apply to a pregnant woman during normal pregnancy?		
medical caring role	0	0
midwifery caring role	22	39.29
both	34	60.71
Did you augment the labor force to fasten delivery?		
Yes	40	71.43
Not always	7	12.5
No	9	16.07
Did you stay with the woman in a birthing room during labor?		
Yes	56	100
Monitor in the office	0	0
Not always	0	0

Table 4: Practice of the midwifery model of care among midwives

Table 5: Factors affecting the utilization of the midwifery care model

Items	SA	A	N	D	SD	X	Remark
Inadequate midwife knowledge and confidence	10	5	26	6	5	2.95	Disagreed
Healthcare system barriers, e.g., access issues	31	19	0	6	0	4.34	Agreed
Barriers to social and political factors, such as sociocultural practices and political instability	40	15	0	0	1	4.66	Agreed
Unavailability of midwives	39	0	14	3	0	4.34	Agreed
Lack of funding in the healthcare system	46	3	5	0	2	4.62	Agreed
Stakeholders' Resistant Attitudes	30	14	2	9	1	4.13	Agreed